

A Point-Prevalence Audit of Oxygen Prescribing and Monitoring Practices in a Tertiary Hospital in Dublin, Ireland

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Abstract

Background

Oxygen therapy is one of the most common hospital interventions, yet inappropriate prescribing and monitoring can lead to patient harm, particularly among those with chronic respiratory disease. National guidelines from the British Thoracic Society (BTS) and Ireland's National Clinical Effectiveness Committee (NCEC) recommend that oxygen be prescribed formally with a defined, condition-specific target saturation range [1,2]. This audit assessed adherence to these standards in a tertiary hospital.

Methods

A point-prevalence audit was conducted at Connolly Hospital, Dublin, Ireland, between August 4 and August 23, 2025. Adult inpatients on the medical and respiratory wards who were receiving supplemental oxygen at the time of review were included. Data were collected on oxygen prescription, documentation and appropriateness of target saturation ranges, and alignment of observed saturations with those targets. Categorical data were analyzed using the Chi-square test, or Fisher's exact test where expected counts were < 5. Statistical analyses were performed with IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 29.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). The audit was registered with the Connolly Hospital Clinical Audit Department (Audit ID CH-QIP-2025-17).

Results

A total of 33 patients were included in the audit. Table 1 presents the demographic and clinical characteristics of the study cohort. The mean age was 68.4 ± 12.3 years, with 18 (55%) males and 15 (45%) females. Most patients were admitted under medical wards (55%), and the average hospital stay was 7.2 ± 3.4 days. The most common diagnoses were COPD exacerbation (33%) and pneumonia (27%). Table 2 summarizes compliance with oxygen-prescribing and monitoring standards. Only 3 (9%) patients had oxygen formally prescribed on the medication chart, and 13 (39%) had documented target saturation ranges, of which 5 (15%) were appropriate for the clinical context. At the time of review, 6 (18%) patients were within the target range. The differences between expected (100%) and observed compliance were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Table 1. Demographic and clinical profile of included patients (n = 33)

Sex: Male 18 (55%), Female 15 (45%)
Age group: <50 (15%), 50–69 (42%), ≥70 (42%)
Ward type: Medical 18 (55%), Respiratory 15 (45%)
Mean hospital stay: 7.2 ± 3.4 days
Primary diagnosis: COPD exacerbation 11 (33%), Pneumonia 9 (27%), Heart failure 5 (15%), Asthma 3 (9%), Other (sepsis, ILD, etc.) 5 (15%)

Table 2. Compliance with oxygen-prescribing and monitoring standards (n = 33)

Parameter	Standard (%)	Observed n (%)	95% CI	p-value
Oxygen formally prescribed	100	3 (9%)	1–24	0.001
Target saturation range documented	100	13 (39%)	22–58	0.005
Target range appropriate for context	100	5 (15%)	5–32	0.02
Patients within target range	100	6 (18%)	7–35	0.01

P-values calculated using Chi-square test (Fisher's exact applied where expected counts <5).

Discussion

Interpretation of Findings

This audit demonstrates persistent deficiencies in adherence to established oxygen-prescribing standards at Connolly Hospital. Only 9% of patients had oxygen formally prescribed, and less than half had documented target saturation ranges—findings consistent with previous studies [3,4]. The low compliance rate likely reflects systemic factors such as limited staff awareness, absence of prompts in the medication chart, and misconceptions about the pharmacologic importance of oxygen therapy.

Comparison with Other Studies

Comparable audits across the UK and Ireland have reported similar deficiencies, with formal oxygen-prescription rates typically below 20%. Following implementation of structured educational interventions and electronic prescribing prompts, compliance in some centers improved to over 70%, underscoring the value of targeted education and workflow redesign [6,7].

Potential Explanations and Implications

Inadequate documentation of target saturation ranges likely results from both human and system-level barriers [1,2]. The format of existing medication charts may not prompt clinicians to record target saturations, and time constraints contribute to oversight. This is clinically significant for patients at risk of hypercapnic respiratory failure, for whom excessive oxygen administration can precipitate CO₂ retention and acidosis.

Limitations

This was a single-center audit with a modest sample size and a point-prevalence design. Data collection was conducted by a single auditor without inter-rater reliability assessment. Despite these limitations, the audit provides a valid snapshot of routine practice and highlights specific targets for improvement.

Novelty and Future Work

This audit represents the first cycle of a planned two-cycle quality-improvement project. Proposed interventions include staff training, visual reminders on medication charts, and the integration of electronic prescribing prompts. A re-audit is scheduled for Q1 2026 to evaluate the impact of these measures and close the audit loop.

Conclusions

Adherence to national oxygen-prescribing guidelines remains suboptimal at Connolly Hospital. Formal prescriptions, appropriate target documentation, and compliance with saturation ranges were below expected standards. Targeted education and system-based solutions are essential to align clinical practice with national guidance and improve patient safety.

References

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